

Influencing factors of smoking behavior among adolescents: A literature review

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 101–104

Publication history: Received on 22 April 2021; revised on 28 May 2023; accepted on 31 May 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1020>

Abstract

Introduction: Smoking is a behavior that causes many problems, especially health problems. However, the number of smokers in Indonesia keeps increasing, including adolescents smokers. Although regulations have been made to reduce smoking behavior, the Indonesian people still continue to smoke.

Method: This research method used literature reviews from PubMed and Google Scholar published between 2013 and 2021.

Results and Discussion: The results of this study indicate that the influencing factors of smoking behavior among adolescents are the influence of friends (four articles), the influence of family (three articles), curiosity (two articles), stress level (one article), and lack of strict regulations regarding smoking behavior (one article).

Conclusion: Factors that influence adolescents to smoke are the influence of friends, family influence, curiosity and trial and error, stress levels, and lack of application of regulations regarding smoking behavior.

Keywords: Smoking; Behavior; Influence; Adolescents

1. Introduction

Smoking is a behavior that causes many problems, especially health problems. However, the number of smokers in Indonesia keeps increasing. The prevalence of smokers aged 15 and over in Indonesia is 32.2% (1). Meanwhile, the percentage of adolescent smokers aged 13-15 in Indonesia is 18.8% and 39.6% of adolescents in Indonesia have ever smoked (2). In addition, based on Basic Health Research 2018, the prevalence of smoking behavior among adolescents aged 10-18 in 2018 was 9.1% and increased compared to the prevalence in 2013, which was 7.2% (13).

Smoking behavior cause many problems, especially health problems. Health problems that can be caused by smoking are stroke, ischemic heart disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, diabetes mellitus, and lung cancer (1). And more than 22,000 people die every day due to tobacco use (3). This is caused by the chemicals in cigarettes. These chemicals are nicotine, protein, starch, pectin, cellulose, sugar, resin, essential oils, organic acids, and chlorophyll, santophyll, and carotene dyes (4). Many studies have shown that these chemicals cause dangerous diseases.

The Indonesian government has made several policies related to smoking, such as the cigarette excise policy and the No Smoking Area (KTR). The cigarette excise tax policy is implemented nationally so that the price of cigarettes is not affordable for the community. While the KTR regulations have been implemented by 67% of 517 cities in Indonesia (1).

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Despite all of those regulations, the Indonesian people still continue to smoke, even the adolescents. Therefore, this study was conducted to find out more about the influencing factors of smoking behavior among adolescents

2. Material and methods

The methods of this study is literature review. The literature review is a method that summarizing journal articles, books, and other documents about the topic. This study used journal article sources accessed through Google Scholar and PubMed. Journal articles were searches with the keywords “behavior”, “smoking”, and “adolescents”. From the search, eight journal articles were obtained, both from national and international journals.

3. Results and discussion

Based on a search of the articles collected and the author's analysis, it was found that:

Table 1 List of articles

No	Author	Research Title	Country	Method	Instrument	Result
1.	Nicole Clancy, Nicholas Zwar and Robyn Richmond ⁽⁵⁾	Depression, Smoking, and Smoking Cessation: A Qualitative Study	Australia	Qualitative research	In-depth semi-structured interviews (Questions about smoking experiences)	There is a strong relation between smoking behavior and depression
2.	Fithria, Muhammad Adlim, Syarifah Rauzatul Jannah, and Teuku Tahlil ⁽⁶⁾	Indonesian Adolescents' Perspectives on Smoking Habits: A Qualitative Study	Indonesia	Qualitative research	Focus Group Discussion (Questions about smoking experiences)	The reason of smoking habit in society are the influence of friends, curiosity, parents, and symbol of masculinity
3.	M. Ridwan and Andy Amir ⁽⁷⁾	Qualitative Study of Smoking Behavior among Employees of Raden Mattaher Hospital Jambi	Indonesia	Qualitative research	In-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion (Questions about smoking experiences)	The lack of strict application on the No Smoking Area (KTR) regulation
4.	Yunus Elon and Evelin Malinti ⁽⁸⁾	The Phenomenon of Smoking among Adolescents: A Qualitative Study	Indonesia	Qualitative research	Triangulation (participant observation, in-depth interviews, and documentary data collection)	Reason for adolescents to smoke are curiosity, friends, and parents. Adolescents' views on somkers are cool, confident, and look mature
5.	Devie Hangriani Patana and Yunus Elon ⁽⁹⁾	Smoking Phenomenon in Female Adolescent: A Qualitative Study	Indonesia	Qualitative research	Interview (questions about smoking experiences)	The reasons why informants smoke are the influence of friends, wanting to try, and curiosity
6.	Sih Martini ⁽¹⁰⁾	The Meaning of Smoking among	N/A	Qualitative research	In-depth interview	The meaning of smoking among adolescent girls are

		Adolescent Female Smokers				symbol of cool and rebellion person, reducing burden, and a way to get pleasure.
7.	Fathin Faridah ⁽¹¹⁾	Analysis of Causing Factor of Adolescent Smoking Behavior at SMK "X" Surakarta	Indonesia	Quantitative research (Cross sectional)	Questionnaire	Factors associated with smoking behavior are lack of knowledge, negative attitudes, easy access to cigarettes, family support, peer support, teacher support, and low exposure to smoking ban regulations at school
8.	Muhammad Rachmat, Ridwan Mochtar Thaha, and Muhammad Syafar ⁽¹²⁾	Smoking Behavior of Junior High School Students	Indonesia	Quantitative research (Cross sectional)	Structured questionnaire	There is a relation between peer group interaction, family interaction, and cigarette advertising with adolescent smoking behavior

Based on the 8 selected articles described in the following paragraphs, the discussion section will discuss factors that influence smoking behavior among adolescents:

Many studies have been conducted to determine the factors that influence smoking behavior among adolescents. Some of the reasons adolescents start smoking are the influence of friends, seeing parents, and curiosity (8).

The influence of friends is the factor that influences most of smoking behavior (12). Adolescents smoke because of the encouragement from friends (6). 50.6% of the respondent in high school in Surakarta first smoked because of friends' invitation (11). The influence of friends is very important because adolescents' lives are very dependent on their peers. Their peers' behavior will encourage adolescents to do the same behavior.

Besides the influence of friends, family influence is one of the factors that influence smoking behavior among adolescents. 90% of adolescent smokers have parents who smoke (9). Parents are figures who set an example for children. Other than that, the family is the first "school" for children. Therefore, the smoking behavior of parents and family has an influence on smoking behavior among adolescents.

The influence of friends and family is related to the next factor, curiosity. The adolescents' curiosity arise when they see their friends or family smoking. Study in Aceh Besar shows that there is a relation between adolescent curiosity and their smoking behavior (6). Curiosity then leads adolescents to try smoking. A study conducted in Paropngpong District showed that 40% of their respondents smoked starting from trying (9). In addition, this is also supported by adolescents' views on smoking behavior. Adolescents considered that smoking behavior is a cool behavior (10). So, when teenagers see their friends smoking and think it is cool, they then try to smoke.

In addition to these factors, factors that can influence a person to smoke are mental conditions and mood disorders (5). This is in line with the results of research on adolescent female smokers that cigarettes are considered as an escape and stress reliever (9). Adolescents interpret cigarettes as a carrier of pleasure and can reduce burdens (10).

In another study, one of the factors that makes someone continues to smoke is due to the lack of supervision of no smoking area (7). As known, Indonesia has established regulations on Non-Smoking Areas (KTR). However, these regulations have not been implemented optimally so that smokers can still smoke, even in No Smoking Areas (KTR). For adolescents, it is also important that regulations related to smoking prohibition are implemented in schools. Smoking ban regulations in schools have little impact on students' smoking behavior (11). The lack of impact of school

regulations can also be caused by the lack of supervision and the lack of strict punishments given to students and other school residents who smoke.

4. Conclusion

From the literature review that has been done, it can be concluded that the factors that can influence adolescents to smoke are the friends' influence, family's influence, curiosity, stress levels, and lack of application of regulations related to smoking behavior. Friends' influence is the most influential factor on adolescent smoking behavior. Therefore, cooperation between family, school, and government is needed to provide supervision, education, and increase the implementation of regulations related to smoking behavior. Peer support programs can also be created to reduce smoking behavior in adolescents because peer influence is the most influential factor in adolescent smoking behavior.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the reviewer's positive suggestion on this paper.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no differences of opinion among the authors on the publication of this paper.

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